

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF PLANNING EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES BASED ON A PERSON - ORIENTED APPROACH IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: In this article, in order to achieve the desired development and prosperity of the world community, the need for information technology (IT) is growing at a great pace, as well as detailed information about the work being done to further develop digital and electronic services in rural areas.

Keywords: e-commerce, e-commerce, e-pay, Uzbekistan, smart contracts, block chain technologies.

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One of the main ideas of modern specialists in pedagogical sciences is the need to study new methods of conducting educational work, complete trends, optimal needs, cognitive needs of parents. Innovations in Pre-School Education The ubiquitous search for an experimental and creative understanding of established educational traditions, the "pseudo-nuclear" problem is acute, with methodological practices characterized by the originality of the form and the originality of the form. is described. Therefore, it is difficult for even teachers with many years of practice to ensure the implementation of consistent innovations in the work of experimental pedagogical places and preschool organizations.

Preschool education experts agree that the creation and implementation of innovative ideas in the educational system is a necessary condition for the development of a modern kindergarten. In connection with financing, the inclusion of innovative organizational solutions in the daily routine of state institutions "When money goes to a preschool teacher" significantly increases the reputation of the institution and determines the further directions of development. The introduction of innovative technologies in the educational process, taking into account the psychophysical age characteristics, is always positively perceived by preschool teachers, they easily change activities. In turn, the initiative pedagogical composition Parent community, the need to improve the mechanisms of interaction of kindergarten students with their families is also important. Experts say that innovative technologies in the states are not only possible, but also necessary. However, it should be remembered that pedagogical technologies can be used in

the educational process of preschool children, given several strict requirements. These include:

Conceptuality means that the learning process should be based on a certain scientific understanding.

Technologies belonging to the system, these technologies must have all the characteristics of the system. That is, they must be integral, logical and their elements must be components - interrelated.

Processing - the pedagogical team must understand the possibility of setting certain goals, planning the educational process, correcting one or another moment during the work process.

Reproducibility means that the technology should be equally effective regardless of the teacher's identity applied to the requirement.

In recent years, modern innovative IT technology has taken a dominant position and is widely used to organize direct teaching-methodical work in preschool education. Teachers who have successfully mastered computer literacy can open up a wide range of opportunities for students, and this is not limited to showing presentations and teaching videos. In the conditions of a huge selection of locally developed programs, it is very difficult for parents to choose something that fully meets the age and educational needs of the child. Getting a competent opinion on this issue allows creating optimal conditions for activity, developing children, creating the necessary things to establish effective cooperation with family representatives of family representatives, increasing the authority of the teacher in the eyes of parents.

The demands placed on the education of our country mean that, as in foreign countries, it is necessary to attract the best practices aimed at improving the quality of education by evaluating and monitoring the development of the fields of education and science. Formation of intellectual activity of the young generation has become an important issue not only for a specific country, but also for the international community. Therefore, many international organizations have put into practice international evaluation programs such as PIRLS, TIMSS, PISA, TALIS, etc. in the field of education, with issues such as the quality of education, assessment of the quality of education. The level of reading and understanding of the text of primary school students consists in identifying and evaluating the specific features in the educational system that cause students to achieve different achievements.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

One of the reforms in education can be seen in the adoption of DTS (2017) based on the competence approach, and in it, the qualification requirements for students in the field of reading in primary education are based on international

experiences. It includes the competences of analyzing an artistic work close to the requirements of PIRLS international studies:

- can understand the meanings of words and sentences in the text;
- can be affected by the content of the work; can distinguish examples of folk art;
- can distinguish the name, author, content and characters of studied works;
- can relate to the characters of the work; can answer questions and tasks related to the content of the read work.

In the previous educational programs, the evaluation process determined only the amount of knowledge remembered, and in the new program, the skills formed by students are evaluated.

The development of reading literacy around the world is directly related to why people read. These reasons include studying for pleasure and personal interest, or to participate meaningfully in education and community life. Most students' first reading is often a story (such as story collections or picture books) or informational texts that provide students with information about the world around them and answer questions.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The main problem in preparing students for PIRLS international studies in primary education is that the current 3-4th grade "Reading Book" textbooks are old-fashioned and lack a modern approach. First of all, "Reading" textbooks should be created in accordance with excellent international assessment programs, that is, texts should be focused on demonstrating how children can apply the acquired information to situations.

CONCLUSION

It is necessary to start preparing for participation in international evaluation programs with the study of international experiences in this field, as well as with the creation of a new generation of textbooks. This guarantees that the quality of education will increase and that Uzbekistan will achieve high results at the level of international standards.

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